

Influence of Learners' Expressive Language on their Performance in English Composition in Primary Schools, Eldoret West Sub County

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Abstract:

The main purpose of the paper was Influence of Learners' Expressive Language on Their Performance in English Composition in Primary Schools, Eldoret West Sub County, Kenya. This study was based on Acculturation Theory. Descriptive survey research design was utilized in this study. The target population comprised a total of 8395 standard 7 pupils and 326 teachers of English. Participants were selected by simple random sampling technique. A total of 316 pupils were selected for the study. Moreover, two teachers of English from the sampled 21 schools were purposively selected giving 42 teachers. Total of 358 participants was selected. Structured questionnaires were used as the main data collection instruments in this study as well as interview guides and document analysis. The researcher used descriptive statistics; proportions, percentages, and means to establish the relationships among variables. The study further used Pearson correlation to test the relationship between determinants and performance in English composition. Interview guide data was analyzed qualitatively under thematic areas defined by the objectives. The correlation model illustrated indicates a significant positive relationship between expressive language and the performance in Composition writing ($r= 0.235$ and $p\text{-value}=0.000<\alpha=0.01$). The use of English in communication also makes it easier for learners to express themselves in English. Besides, it is important for teachers always to use English to communicate with learners and in addition, parents should encourage learners to speak English.

Keywords: Learners' Expressive Language, Performance, English Composition, Primary Schools, teachers. Pupils

Introduction

Groenewegen (2008), notes that skills in composition writing enable the pupil with the means by which the exposition of ideas and responses to given tasks can be tackled within the communicative nature of a language. The composition is defined as a piece of writing made up of one or more paragraphs talking about a definite theme or subject (Bereiter & Scardamalia, 2013). Mojina (2010) asserts that writing is not easy nor is it an impulsive activity because it needs some sentient mental effort. Further, he indicated that it involves 'thinking out' sentences and discovering ways of combining and arranging words. A good composition is composed of an introduction, body, and conclusion (Bereiter and Scardamalia, 2013).

Writing English composition gives the learners opportunity to be adventurous with the language (Mojina, 2010). Gallagher (2010) asserts that the educators of English dialect who instruct in schools know about the challenges required during the time spent figuring out how to ace the diverse sorts of writing assignments and how to create genuinely intelligent, exact, significant and appropriate composition. In an undeniably requesting universe of education, the significance of guaranteeing learners' capability in writing abilities cannot be overemphasized. The ability to write well, hitherto a luxury is now a dire necessity (Gallagher, 2010). Writing is crucial to learners' creating proficiency abilities. In light of this, instructing learners to compose well ought to be the best need of an advantageous training framework. According to Gallagher (2006), a school that shows its learners the educational programs without simultaneously showing them how to compose well is a school that has fizzled.

In some schools in the United States, Hesse (2010) stated that learner's composition lack variety in their expressing of ideas. Sentences are long and meaningless and include wrongly used conjunctions while the complex ones which are correct lack variety. Learners show there is no or absence of understanding of the difference between fragments and short sentences. They confuse the two thereby messing compositions with meaningful fragments. Dawson (2014) observed that most ordinary level learners don't have the foggiest idea about the different sorts of compositions. These are, graphic, contentious, account and descriptive. He additionally countered that absence of information on sorts of articles make numerous learners give differentiating gadgets to an alternative paper.

In spite of the fact that the general target for writing in upper elementary school expects that toward the finish of the grade school course the learner ought to have the capacity to convey fluidly, autonomously and precisely in their regular day to day existence (Kenya Institute of Education, 2002), performance in composition in national examination remains unsatisfactory as evidenced by KNEC reports on Kenya Certificate of Primary Education (KCPE) examination (refer to table 1). KNEC reports indicate that in writing tasks, learners show carelessness in such basics as punctuation, spelling and sentence construction.

In Table 1.1 the performance in English composition in both the KCPE examination and the Eldoret West sub-county evaluation tests in the last five years is presented. English language objective scores have also been indicated for comparison. The scores show a below average performance, which has also been fluctuating, recording a maximum mark of 47 %. In the five year period, the performance has registered between 34 and 42 % in the national examination and between 40 and 47 % in the sub-county examination.

Table 1.1: Composition Performance Index of KCPE and Mock Exams of Eldoret West Sub-County, 2011-2015

Year	Paper	KCPE	Sub-County evaluation
		Mean %	Mean%
2011	Obj	49.12	53.58
	Comp	34.16	40.48
2012	Obj	47.1	56.02
	Comp	42.45	44.68
2013	Obj	46.1	56.88
	Comp	42.43	47.47
2014	Obj	45.9	51.1
	Comp	41.9	39.43
2015	Obj	45.3	48.74
	Comp	41.45	41.9

Source (KNEC-KCPE Newsletter, 2015)

The above statistical records on the decline of performance in composition writing can hinder the performance of pupils, particularly in English subject. In addition, this can affect overall performance and hence a concern to parents, teachers, and KNEC. despite the problem, there has been a paucity of studies on primary schools. This study departed from the aforementioned studies by going lower to the basic level of the education system, namely primary school, where pupils, not only undergo English language acquisition but use as a language of instruction and evaluation. Along these lines, it against this background the present review looked to examine the determinants of learners' execution in English composition among pupils in primary schools, Eldoret West Sub County, Kenya.

Theoretical Framework

This study was based on Acculturation Theory. This is a naturally arranged hypothesis proposed by John Schumann in 1978. It was utilized as a part of 1980 in the field of Linguistics, accurately, Second Language Acquisition. It expresses that Second Language Acquisition is the aftereffect of cultural assimilation, which he characterizes as "the social and mental reconciliation of the learner with the objective dialect (TL) gathering" (Schumann, 1978). The significant claim of the hypothesis is that cultural assimilation, which is a bunch of social-mental components, is the real reason for Second Language Acquisition (Schumann, 1990). Schumann expresses that any learner can be set along a continuum going from social-mental separation to social-mental nearness with the speakers of the objective dialect. The level of dialect procurement, then, would relate to the level of the learner's nearness to the objective gathering. In this manner, the cultural assimilation hypothesis contends that learners will be fruitful in Second Language Acquisition if there are less social and mental separations amongst them and the speakers of the second dialect. A portion of the variables that record for the securing of the second dialect as indicated by the hypothesis includes: inspiration and state of mind of the learner, constrained joining of social gatherings and how tight-weave the gathering is.

The Acculturation theory likewise discusses part of the educator as a genuine reader, mentor, and evaluator. Feedback on the way educators react to learners' compositions emerges from the way that they appear to focus more on their part as evaluators and judges and not mentors. This implies educators are believed to judge learners' work as opposed to guiding learners through their composition. In process writing, the result of the composition is the fate of an auxiliary concern, and the instructor turns into a facilitator in giving developmental input amid the procedure of every learner's written work. The Instructor's input given is joined amid the procedure rather than the conventional evaluation that concentrates on the last written item. An arrangement of appraisal that spotlights just on the final composed item gives hazy criticism on what learners can do as journalists (Kasule & Lunga, 2010). According to Atetwe (2013), a portion of the elements that record for the securing of the second dialect as per the hypothesis includes inspiration and demeanor of the learner, constrained incorporation of social gatherings and how tight-sew the gathering is. This hypothesis connected to this review since it tried to discover how utilization of a dialect in a social setting impacts piece of writing. The hypothesis additionally demonstrates that learners will be effective in creative composing if there are less social and mental components. This review tried to set up the impact showing strategies, reading propensities and student's expressive dialect impacts performance in the writing of composition.

Review of Related Literature

According to Cummins (2000), learners need control of formal English with a specific end goal to do well in English exams. They additionally contend that dialect creates through bona fide dialect utilize. According to Cummins (2000) schools have a duty to give a wide "scope of encounters that will encourage dialect improvement for social collaboration, performing very in English and in addition dialect for scholarly purposes." This clarifies why schools have instruments to check native language talking. In this review, the scientist needed to discover a portion of the systems that were set up by schools to control the utilization of primary languages and whether these components worked.

The conduct and classroom cooperation of teachers and understudies assume an imperative part in the fruitful execution of informative dialect educating in EFL settings. In the CLT classroom, it is by all accounts understudy focused which does not rely on upon their instructors constantly, sitting tight for guidelines and expressions of endorsement, adjustment, exhortation or acclaim (Jones, 2007; Ozsevik, 2010; Chang, 2011). They don't overlook each other, however, take a gander at each other and speak with each other. They esteem each other's commitments; they participate, gain from each other and help each other with a specific end goal to achieve the objective of correspondence (Jones, 2007; Ozsevik, 2010; Chang, 2011). At the point when in

trouble or in uncertainty, they don't instantly approach the instructor for help or guidance, however simply after they have attempted to take care of the issue among themselves with an accentuation on cooperating in sets, gatherings and all in all class. In the meantime, the educator's part in the CLT classroom goes about as a facilitator or teacher, who controls the understudies, deals with their exercises, and guides their learning procedure so as to build up their dialect aptitudes (Jones, 2007; Ozsevik, 2010; Chang, 2011).

Similarly, Ozsevik (2010) and Chang (2011) contend that learners in CLT classrooms should take an interest in classroom exercises that depend on a collective, as opposed to individualistic, way to deal with learning. They are depicted as dynamic members in the dialect learning process (Ozsevik, 2010, Chang, 2011; Jones, 2007). In addition, CLT as a methodology has much to do with interaction (Breen and Candlin, 1980; Doherty & Singh, 2005). Likewise, it is astute to claim that an instructor's and understudies' parts in the CLT classroom are a dynamic element and consequently they have a tendency to shift constantly (Jones, 2007; Ozsevik, 2010, Chang, 2011)

In a few reviews, EFL and ESL educators communicated troubles in including social perspectives into their classes due to need involvement in an English-speaking nation (Yu, 2001; Liao, 2004). Students' resistance and low-English proficiency also deter teachers from using communicative language teaching (CLT) (Li, 1998; Liao, 2000; Yu, 2001; Liao, 2004; Chang, 2011). These situational elements may debilitate the teachers' endeavors to utilize CLT. Regardless of whether teachers confront troubles in actualizing CLT in EFL settings, it is important to include their voices the exchange. To expand the quantity of learners who can viably impart in English, national dialect training approaches in numerous EFL nations have moved towards CLT since the 1990s (Littlewood, 2007).

Adebayo (2008) utilized a study configuration to look at the impact of the first language on the execution of English dialect in Junior School Certificate Examination in Western Nigeria. He found that the first language impacts the learners' execution in English dialect in Junior School Certificate Examination in Western Nigeria. He suggests that the English language ought to be utilized as a medium of correspondence inside and outside the classroom and both instructors and learners ought to attempt to enhance their capability level of the dialect which will result in the long run prompt enhanced execution. Adebayo's review does not expressly show to what degree primary language impact the execution; this review looked to build up what Adebayo (2008) neglected to catch in his review by examining the degree to which primary language impacts execution of English.

Kolawole (2002) likewise affirmed that learners' execution in English dialect in optional schools of Nigeria was extremely poor. He focused on further that the standard was poor because of various reasons, for example, the utilization of the first language; a few learners don't comprehend punctuation due to overutilization of primary language in accounting for themselves. This may be consistent with Kenyan case particularly in day schools where learners are drawn from a neighborhood setting of a commonplace local dialect Miguda-Attyang (2003), researches the mentality of Sheng as a rising dialect among the general population of Nairobi. The review uncovers that the state of mind towards Sheng is to a great extent negative. Sheng speakers are considered as awkward in both Kiswahili and English. Another vital perception that Miguda makes is that Kiswahili has a critical part as a national dialect and the most widely used language for the Kenyan populace.

Chai (2000) asserts that the Standard language is maintained through the elaboration of its functions. It inculcates literacy in that writing is easy, and the rules of correctness are envisaged through the education system. Bure, (2006) argues that there is need to connect with the young generation and with what the target audience understands best. If needed, this argument can have negative effects on written and spoken English since as Friedman and Rowl (1980) puts it; learners come with different varieties of language due to their background.

Material and methods

This study adopted descriptive survey design. The target population comprised a total of 8395 standard 7 pupils and 326 teachers of English.. the study used 30% to select pupils from the zone. Participants were selected by simple random sampling technique (Creswell, 2008). Moreover, two teachers of English from the sampled 21 schools were purposively selected giving a total of 42 teachers. Thus, a total of 358 participants were selected. The research instruments used were questionnaires, interview guides, and document analysis. To ascertain the reliability, the questionnaires were pre-tested through a pilot study. The items were selected for the Cronbach's Alpha analysis while ensuring that the model is checked. Quantitative data collected through were analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques. The researcher also used inferential statistics Pearson correlation to show the relationships that exist between the variables. Interviews were basically transcribed and qualitatively analyzed through themes.

Findings

This section presents analysis, interpretation, and discussion of the findings of the study as set out in the research objectives and research methodology.

Sample characteristics

It is evident from the figure that majority of the respondents (54%) were male whereas (46%) of the respondents are female. This tentatively implies that there were more male pupils in public primary schools in Eldoret West Sub-County compared to the female pupils. Most of the learners are young hence are much better than the adult ones in acquiring vocabulary and speaking English more fluently. The above assumption is based on the common belief that the earlier, the better in language learning (Nirmala, 2012). It is evident from the findings that 29.4% of the parents/guardians' have college as their highest level of education, 26.1% university, 20.9% secondary, 13.1% primary and 10.5% other levels of education.

Influence of Pupil's Expressive Language on Learners' Performance in English Composition

The third objective was to assess Pupil's expressive language on learners' performance in English composition where the responses on the objective were presented in figure 4.5, Figure 1, figure 2 and table 3.

Language used more often

As part of the study objective, the researcher sought to establish the language used more often. Figure 4.5 illustrates the results. From the figure, 30.1% of the learners use Kiswahili, 26.5% Sheng, 22.2% English and 21.2% mother tongue. Compared to other languages, English is not used as often as it should be. Kiswahili takes the lion's share in terms of language use followed by Sheng and lastly mother tongue. The implication is that learners have low proficiency in the English language and this could negatively impact on their writing skills.

One of the head teachers said,

"Most of the teachers are role models for pupils in terms of English proficiency since pupils opportunities for interaction with English-speaking users are very limited and it is fundamental for learners to be exposed to oral input as much as possible."

Figure 1: Language used more often

Language(s) mostly used by teachers when talking to learners outside the classroom

The study also sought to establish the language used by teachers mostly when talking to learners outside the classroom. As evidenced in figure 4.6, 70% (215) of the respondents noted that the teachers use English, 21% (64) Kiswahili and 9% (27) mother tongue.

One of the head teachers indicated that:

“Pupils should be punished for speaking in the tongue to help them improve performance in writing composition.”

Figure 2: Language(s) mostly used by teachers when talking to learners outside the classroom

Using the English Language during Conversations

The study sought to establish if learners like using the English language during conversations. Figure 4.6 shows that majority (65%) of the learners do not like using the English language during conversations.

Figure 3: Using the English Language during Conversations

Learners' Expressive Language

This section of the analysis highlights the results on learners' expressive language. The findings are as presented in table 1. The results from the study revealed that, of the total respondents, 47.4% disagreed and 25.2% strongly disagreed that they always express themselves in English while 52.6% agreed and 7.8% strongly agreed. The item realized a mean of 2.35 and standard deviation of 0.944 suggesting that learners rarely expressed themselves in English.

In determining whether learners find themselves most of the time using Kiswahili language when communicating with their peers, the study revealed that; 16.3% of the respondents 2.9% strongly agreed while 83.7% disagreed and 68% strongly disagreed. The results also showed a mean of 1.51 and a standard deviation of 0.835. The results suggest that learners do not use Kiswahili most of the times to communicate with their peers.

In regards to whether the learners' parents always encourage them to speak to them in English, results from the study revealed that, the question had a mean of 2.88 and standard deviation of 1.169. This was as a result of 68.3% of the respondents answering in the affirmative (41.2% strongly agreed), and 31.7% disagreed (21.6% strongly disagreed). In order to find out whether, the learners speak in Sheng when at home; respondents were asked to state the degree to which they concurred with the above. Of the total respondents, 82.7% disagreed and 77.5% strongly disagreed while 17.3% agreed and 9.8% strongly agreed. The item realized a mean of 1.5 and a standard deviation of 0.996 an indication that the learners do not speak in Sheng while at home.

Finally, a related item on whether it is easier for learners to express themselves in Kiswahili than in any other language, of the total respondents, 94.4% agreed, and 72.2% strongly agreed while only 5.6% disagreed. This position was further confirmed by the 3.63 question mean and standard deviation of 0.69. Cognate to the results, Cummins (2000) elucidates that pupils need to have control over formal English so that they are able to excel in examinations. Thus, whenever pupils often use their mother tongue, their written English is significantly influenced negatively.

Table 1:

Learners' Expressive Language

		SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Deviation
I always using express myself in English	Freq.	77	68	137	24	2.35	0.944
	%	25.2	22.2	44.8	7.8		
Most of the time I find myself using Kiswahili language when communicating with my peers	Freq.	208	48	41	9	1.51	0.835
	%	68	15.7	13.4	2.9		
My parents always encourage me to speak to them in English	Freq.	66	31	83	126	2.88	1.169
	%	21.6	10.1	27.1	41.2		
When am at home, most of the time I speak in sheng	Freq.	237	16	23	30	1.5	0.996
	%	77.5	5.2	7.5	9.8		
It easier to express me in Kiswahili than in any other language	Freq.	10	7	68	221	3.63	0.69
	%	3.3	2.3	22.2	72.2		

Learners' expressive language was found to have a positive and significant influence on their performance in English Composition. Further support to the study findings is by Adebayo (2008) who found out that mother tongue affects the learners' performance in the English language in Junior School Certificate Examination in

Western Nigeria. The author recommends the use of English language as a medium of communication within and outside the classroom in an attempt to improve their proficiency level of the language which will eventually lead to improved performance. Additionally, the findings are also in tally with that of Kolawole (2002) confirming that learners' performance in the English language in Secondary schools in Nigeria was very poor due to the use of mother tongue.

In this section of the analysis, the study highlights teachers' responses. Table 2 illustrates the results.

Teachers were asked whether pupils always express themselves in English. The results from the study revealed that, of the total respondents, 8.3% (3) strongly agreed that students always express themselves in English, 11.1% (4) of them agreed, 50% (18) disagreed and 30.6% (11) strongly disagreed. The mean value was 2.63 and standard deviation 0.946 revealing that in most occasions pupils did not express themselves in Kiswahili.

In determining whether most of the pupils have a tendency of using Kiswahili language when communicating with their peers, the study revealed that;88.9% (32) of the teachers agreed, 5.5% (2) disagreed while 5.6% (2) of the teachers strongly disagreed. The results summed up to a mean of 3.91 and standard deviation of 0.966. It can, therefore, be said that pupils have a tendency of using Kiswahili to communicate with their peers.

To establish whether teachers encourage pupils to speak to them in English, teachers were asked to state the degree to which they concurred with the above. Of the total teachers, 36.1% (13) of them strongly agreed, 47.2% (17) agreed, 8.4% (3) disagreed, while 8.3% (3) strongly disagreed. The results summed up to a mean of 3.92 and standard deviation of 0.962.

The study further enquired from teachers whether when most pupils are at home and unsupervised speak in Sheng. The results revealed that 19.5% (7) of the respondents strongly agreed, 22.2% agreed, 22.2% (8) disagreed and 36.1% (13) strongly disagreed. The results summed up to a mean of 2.73 and standard deviation of 1.566.

Finally,11.4% (4) of the teachers strongly agreed that it is easier for pupils to express themselves in Kiswahili than in any other language,44.2% (16) of them agreed while 22.2% (8) of the teachers disagreed. The results were supported by a mean of 3.94 and a standard deviation of 0.979.

Table 2:

Teachers response

		SD	D	A	SA	MEAN	SD
My pupils always express themselves in English	Freq.	11	18	4	3	2.63	0.946
	%	30.6	50	11.1	8.3		
Most of the pupils have tendency of using Kiswahili language when communicating with my peers	Freq.	2	2	32	0	3.91	0.966
	%	5.6	5.5	88.9	0		
I always encourage my pupils to speak to them in English	Freq.	3	3	17	13	3.92	0.962
	%	8.3	8.4	47.2	36.1		
When at home or unsupervised, most pupils speak in sheng	Freq.	13	8	8	7	2.73	1.566
	%	36.1	22.2	22.2	19.5		
It easier for pupils to expression Kiswahili than in any other language	Freq.	8	8	16	4	3.94	0.979
	%	22.2	22.2	44.2	11.4		

Performance in the last composition-writing exam

Performance in the last composition-writing exam was sought by the study. Based on the findings in figure 3, 41.2% of the learners had average performance in the last composition writing exam, 26.1% good, 22.9% poor, 6.5% very poor and 3.3% very good.

Figure 3: Performance in the last composition-writing exam

Total marks scored in the last composition-writing exam

The total marks scored by learners in the last composition-writing exam areas presented in figure 4. As evidenced in the figure, 65.7% of the learners scored between 21 to 30%, 16.3% scored between 11 to 10%, 10.5% score between 1 to 10% and 7.5% of the learners scored between 31 to 40%.

Figure 4: Total marks scored in the last composition-writing exam

Correlation Results

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (r) was used to analyze the relationships that are inherent in the independent and dependent variables as well as among the independent variables/ factors. Therefore, a correlation model was computed to identify the relationship between expressive language on the performance of composition writing. The correlation table also shows that there is a significant positive relationship between expressive language and the performance in Composition writing ($r= 0.235$ and $p\text{-value}=0.000 < \alpha=0.01$).

Table 3:

Correlation

		Performance	Expressive language
Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	1	
Expressive language	Pearson Correlation	.235**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Conclusion and Recommendations

learners' expressive language has a significant influence on their performance in English Composition. Therefore, whenever learners frequently use Kiswahili or Sheng as a mode of communication, their written English is impaired. Nevertheless, when teachers use English to communicate with the learners as well as parents encouraging them to speak English, their proficiency level of the English language improves. An increase in the proficiency level is indicative of improved performance in writing composition. On the whole, most of the learners have exhibited average performance in Composition writing. There is thus need for more writing practice, discussions and reading of textbooks on composition writing so as to improve the performance. It is also crucial for the learners to practice the use of the English language by using it to communicate. In so doing, they will find it easier to construct sentences and also learn different ways of expressing themselves. These are important in writing compositions.

There is a well-defined observation that if pupils often use their mother tongue, their written English is negatively affected. Furthermore, pupils require more than social language skills to be successful in school; they also require academic language skills that comprise receptive and productive language, thinking and reasoning. The use of English in communication will also make it easier for learners to express themselves in English. There is also need to expose pupils to excursions, out of which it will serve to expose them to many aspects of life and which generate ideas and enhances creativity. In addition, pupils need exposure to an environment where second language learning is practiced. It is therefore important for teachers to always use English to communicate with learners and for the parents to encourage learners to speak English.

though the researcher has indicated that teaching and learning strategies and learners' expressive language significantly relate with the performance in English Composition, there is no evidence that performance in English Composition is entirely dependent on the two independent variables. As such, further research needs to be carried out to establish what other factors contribute significantly to improved performance in English Composition.

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